

Human Rights Abuses and Its Effects on National Integration in Nigeria: The Role of Religion

Emmanuel Moses Sebu

Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, Benue State University, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria
sebuemma6@gmail.com

Dorcas Mwuese Abagi

Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, Benue State University, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria
dorcasabagi25@gmail.com

Abigail Akpa

Department of Christian Religious Studies, Akawe Torkula Polytechnic, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria
abigailakpa80@gmail.com

Abstract

This study assesses the effects of human rights abuses on national Integration in Nigeria and the role of religion in curbing same. There is a universal consciousness that the human being is different from all other creatures and possesses certain privileges that are inalienable. These inalienable privileges are called human rights and are supposed to be enjoyed by every human person under normal circumstances. However, experience has shown that human beings themselves have at one time or the other in history infringed on the rights of other human beings. Such infringements constitute human rights abuses. In Nigeria especially, the cases of human rights abuses have continued to deteriorate despite the United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights and African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights. People are largely discriminated on the grounds of ethnicity, race, colour, religion, etc. This study therefore seeks to analyse the state of human rights abuses as it hinders national integration in Nigeria and the role of religion in enhancing human rights. This is pertinent as the question of rights cannot be overemphasized in contemporary society. Data for the study are gathered from secondary sources. The study makes use of critical and evaluative methods for analysis. The study recommends that relevant agencies and the major religious bodies in Africa should work conscientiously towards enhancing human rights in Africa. The study concludes that religion has an onerous task to perform towards enhancement of human rights in Nigeria, which would bring about national integration.

Keywords: Human rights, abuses, national integration, religion, Nigeria

Introduction

It is over seventy years after the United Nations adopted the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights and over 40 years after the Organization of African Unity (OAU) adopted its own African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights. However, as Paul J. Magnarella submits, “the human rights situation on the African continent is decidedly bleak,”¹ making the attainment of human rights in Africa a monumental challenge for this century. The scenario becomes more glaring when one considers the reports of various international organizations concerning the position of human rights abuses in Africa. Amnesty International reported that “in 1998 twenty-four African countries had serious and widespread human rights violations occasioned by armed conflicts, social and political unrest.”² The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees estimated that in 1998 there were about 3.5 million refugees in Africa, eighty percent of them women and children under the age of five. In its 1999 survey, Human Rights Watch (HRW) reported that Africa's refugee population had increased to 6.3 million. According to Africa Overview, “Of the ten top refugee producers in the world, five were African: Burundi, Eritrea, Sierra Leone, Somalia, and Sudan.”³

With the above scenario, and given the various declarations on human rights, it becomes a matter to wonder why Africa still wallows in human rights abuses, what the causes of these abuses really are and what could be proffered as panacea to the menace. In this paper, therefore, we shall consider religion in its response to human rights abuses in Africa as well as make some practical suggestions towards curbing human right problems in Africa. This derives from the fact that Africans generally love human life and hold it as sacred and the fact that human rights are founded on respect for the sanctity of life and human dignity, as briefly considered below.

The Value of Human Life in Africa

The African worldwide is originally anthropocentric. In fact, all other beings in the world - spiritual and physical act on the human person to preserve his life. This is why O.U. Kalu remarks that:

African religion and culture are life-enhancing. Human life is held 'sacred' in Africa. It is esteemed as the highest value. This is why the African proverbs, ritual festivals, folklores and other customs are highly loaded with appreciation of life. Life is appreciated as the primordial ground for all human endeavours and aspirations.⁴

Such philosophy of life is expressed in some names like '*Ndubuisi*,' (life is first and foremost), *Ochifije* (Life is greater than wealth), etc. Any abuse of human life is abominable, just like shedding of human blood is categorically abhorred. Thus Michael Apochi observes that, "In many traditional African tribes, the killing of a kinsman, the antithesis of caring for him was not only a crime but also as an abomination. After the murderer had been executed, his family would have to perform sacrifice and rites to remove the stain of evil and ward-off the anger of the gods."⁵ Such beliefs and customs as this make for respect and preservation of life in practical terms. So in Africa, ripe old age is valued as a blessing especially when it is edified with many children, relatives and wealth. Even the poor and the mentally sick are protected and cared for both by the community and the family ties. Here M.O. Ekpenyong is of the opinion that:

The need for social security to feel at 'home' seems to be the reason (for Africans) to search for kinship... in time of need, poverty, sickness, disaster, and death – the welfare of those involved is the happy burden of the family (...) the view of the family guided by hospitality looks down on individualism, selfishness, exploitation, ethnicity, and war. To be cut off from the family is suicidal and death.⁶

Africans show their respect for human life until its natural end. The sacredness of human life especially that of a kinsman has been an edict enshrined in the heart of every African. Commenting on the sacredness of human life, R. Ejimonye and M. Konye aver, "Small wonder the penalty for the transgression of this norm is capital punishment in the original African society... the peoples of Africa respect the life which is conceived and born. They rejoice in this life. They reject the idea that it can be destroyed, even when the so-called 'progressive civilizations' would like to lead them in this direction."⁷

It is an abomination to take someone's life whatever the circumstance. However, the life of enemies and intruders are never revered. In fact, one is patted at the back for killing an intruder. But today, western influence acquired through travels, watching foreign movies, and news have made many Africans to develop a kind of conscience that is not perturbed by homicide and every form of abuse of the human person. Thus husbands abuse or kill their wives and vice versa, parents abuse, and even kill their children in cold blood, and children murder their parents and this trickles down and gets worse in the wider society. The above evils are committed in the face of religion and often even by religious people. At worse, they are aimed at religious people – making them victims in one way or the other. Thus, abuse of the sacredness of human life which is unleashed in the different forms of human rights abuses have emerged as a monstrous challenge to religion in our milieu as we shall notice in the forthcoming section.

Nigerian National Integration

National integration refers to "the awareness of a common identity amongst the citizens of a country".⁸ It means that though we belong to different tribes, castes, religions and regions and speak different languages we

recognize the fact that we are all one. This kind of integration is very important in the building of a strong and prosperous nation. In Nigeria, the need for unity has always been emphasized despite our diversities. Unity in our country does not mean the kind of oneness that comes from racial and cultural similarity. It is as Okeke describes, “unity in spite of great differences, in other words, unity in diversity”.⁹ An important historical event in which this unity was displayed was the freedom movement when all the Indians united against the British rule.

A unique feature of Nigeria is that “almost all the major religions of the world are practiced here like Islam, Christianity, Buddhism, Hinduism, Jainism, and Zoroastrianism”.¹⁰ There are also great varieties in costume, food habits, and social customs. Geographically our land is diverse and there are amazing differences in climate. Despite all these differences Nigeria is a political entity, every part of which is governed under the same Constitution. We have to co-exist with each other peacefully, respect the culture and religion of our fellow Nigerians.

Certain forces or factors have been imbued into the federalism of Nigeria to ensure national integration. The first is the Constitution. Perhaps our founding fathers were aware that there were threats to our unity from various forces. Consequently, certain safeguards were placed in our Constitution. These took the form of certain ideals and principles like democracy, secularism, and social equality that are guaranteed under our Fundamental Rights. Thus, our Constitution is the most important force that promotes national integration.

The concept of secularism is another promoter of national integration in Nigeria. Nigeria is a secular state. This means that each citizen of our country has the right to practice his or her religion. The government cannot show preference to one religion at the expense of another. This has been a very crucial instrument to guarantee freedom of religion in Nigeria. Related to this is the practice of democracy. As a democratic state, all the citizens of Nigeria are equal under the law of the country. Our fundamental rights and directive principles of state policy specifically state that each citizen is equal in every way. People cannot be discriminated against on the basis of differences of sex, religion, language, and culture.

National festivals also act as an important unifying force. Independence Day, Children’s Day, etc. are festivals that are celebrated by all Nigerians and in all parts of the country, regardless of language, religion or culture. They remind us of our common nationality. Our National Symbols like the National Flag, the National Anthem, and the National Pledge also help to remind us that we are all identical. For this reason we stress on the importance of showing proper respect to these symbols. These act as strong unifying forces both in times of celebration and adversity.¹¹

However, in the past there are many forces that have come in the way of our national integration. Often people have very strong feelings about their own religion, ethnic group and language and oppose those of others. Such feelings lead to clashes between different sects. Such occurrences damage our unity and prove to be a hindrance to our progress. Nigeria is an amalgamation of various ethnic groups and tribes. One would have thought that after so many years after the amalgamation our differences would have been cemented. However, even with the passage of time these communal feelings have not ended. More than fifty years after independence communal feelings still exist and riots flare-up every now and then in different parts of the country. This, B.N. Inaku observes is as result of “narrow-mindedness, prejudice, and lack of knowledge of other religions”.¹² This is also because of the exploitation of such feelings by some politicians to further their interests. If we give more importance to our religion rather than our country we cannot contribute to its progress and development.

An Overview of Human Rights Abuse in Nigeria

Decrying the atrocious and horrible human rights abuses that afflict Nigeria today, especially from the perspective of the church’s mission of evangelization, the Synod Fathers posited these provocative elements: “in a continent full of bad news, how is the Christian message a ‘Good News’ for our people? In the midst of an all-pervading despair, where lies the hope and optimism which the Gospel brings?”¹³ The mission of Christ is “Good News” per se. this was what he read out from the scroll of Isaiah to the entire humanity symbolically present in the Jewish community (Isa. 61). An important aspect of that mission of Jesus commissioned by the Holy Spirit says: “He has anointed me to preach the gospel to the poor” (Lk.4).

In the 21st century Nigeria, a country full of potentialities is still plagued by the dilemmas and paradoxes of our contemporary experience. For instance, the violation of the rights and dignity of the human person, poverty, injustice, corruption, religious and civil strife, undemocratic structures, degradation of socio-cultural values, deplorable conditions of working and environmental pollutions seem to be in the increase.

In Nigeria as in many countries of Africa, six decades after independence, our people continue to be excluded from any critical or significant contribution to the world body politics, basic human rights, individual freedom and democratic participation. In the words of P. Kanyandayo:

In June 1990, the Organization of African Unity (O.A.U) launched the popular participation (in the human rights charter) in Addis Ababa; in May 1991 the African leadership forum held in Kampala, Uganda, identified democracy, political pluralism, strict observance of Human Rights, Good Governance, Public Accountability, Popular Participation, Sound Economic Management and Genuine Cooperation as decisive, positive signposts for a good future. If I may ask, what contribution has religion made so far towards the liberation of Africans?¹⁴

Generally, the story of Africa seems to have remained that of a sorry tale. Between 1990 and 1994 in most African countries, at least fourteen Heads of State were fraudulently voted out of power, toppled, exiled or murdered. The frequency of Coups D'état reveals not only the intrigues of colonialism, but also the shallowness of the one-party or "mock-multi party" authoritarian regimes in our society, the unsuitable nature of their methods of government, the human rights abuses in their expression of power and the devaluation of the African esteemed religious values. The question to be asked is: how far has the democratic dispensation improved the human rights situation of the citizenry?

It is not possible to discuss Human Rights abuses without some references to the economy. Whether reasons of management, wrong priorities, false values, or bad planning, the economy of Nigeria is in poor shape and gets worse by the day by all rational indices. Human Rights abuses ranging from child trafficking, prostitution, abortions due to illegal sex, ritual killing, political thuggery, armed robbery, undue assassinations etc., are becoming more and more the order of the day. For Kanyandayo, these are fuelled by elements within the poor nations themselves,

Pockets of local, rich privileged elites and power holders are so positioned that they hold their own fellow citizens in a state of powerless subjection; exploit them through manipulation of power not shared with the majority. Oppression and exploitation of the poor and powerless nations are effected by using these local privileged minorities against their own people.¹⁵

As a result, many Nigerians today are greatly abused and their very rights denied. Many live in abject poverty, while even in the same continents some few individuals are richer than their own country, hence, exploitation and subjection becomes all the more difficult to deal with because of this collusion between local interested minorities and foreign holders of power. This is so evident in the functioning of multinational or transnational companies and in the way the superpowers maintain and support regimes because through them it is easier to keep hold on the poorer countries. It is perhaps such a situation that formed the springboard for the restiveness in the Niger-Delta area of Nigeria. This is another form of neo-colonialism brought through global capitalism.

Ethnicity is also one of the manifestations of Human Rights abuses in Nigeria. Ethnicity is motivated by political, economic, religious and social interest groups.¹⁶ The ethnic bigots acquire and maintain dominance over others, regulate and marginalize others to their advantage and create a sense of superiority. J. H. Cone states openly "ethnicity creates systems of domination and exploitation, sexism, tribalism, classism, religionism and so on. These are structures that breed and maintain all forms of Human Right abuses".¹⁷

Within African culture itself, traces of Human Rights abuses are also found. Most African systems and custom contain abuses of women. In politics although most women participate in the electoral processes as voters, very few are given opportunities to offer themselves as candidates for election. Hence, there is low participation of women in decision-making processes and leadership. This is why H. Okulu laments that, "there are many

issues hindering women participation in politics ranging from the social and the economic to the cultural”.¹⁸ In Nigeria, male chauvinism, the high rate of female illiteracy especially in rural areas, lack of political commitment or consciousness and general lack of infrastructure, has affected other indices such as how responsibilities are shared between men and women, differentiation in training and occupation, differences in attitudes, how men and women perceive themselves. None of these can lead to a proper situation in which a woman can build herself and society. This too is a form of abuse.

These challenges raise the following provocative: Do Nigerian theologians realize what is going on with regards to the dignity of citizens as people created in God’s image? How have they made their voices heard beyond the limits of the altars and pulpits? Is it not intriguing that the rising concerns of some Nigerian theologians over Human Rights result in further enslavement through their imprisonment? Why do Nigerian theologians and pastors manifest disunity among themselves, why have they made themselves powerless? Are they not able to stand their grounds and use the maxim “united we stand, divided we fall?” Is it not unfair that some African theologians have used human conditions such as hunger, wealth, fame, tribe, etc as bait for enslavement and compromise to human rights?

With the above exposition of the position of Human Rights and its various manifestations in Nigeria, one cannot but posit the perturbing question: what are the major causes of these Human Rights abuses plaguing Nigeria? It is the consideration of these causes that would meaningfully pave way for solutions to be proffered to the cankerworm.

Major Causes of Human Rights Abuses

Various factors have been suggested as causes of the protracted Human Rights abuses in Nigeria. However, the list presented by a recent OAU report is quite elaborate. The said report attributed Africa's poor human rights record mainly to factors which include: racism, post-colonialism, poverty, ignorance, disease, religious intolerance, internal conflicts, debt, bad management, corruption, the monopoly of power, the lack of judicial and press autonomy, and border conflicts. Poverty is certainly an endemic factor among the factors. P.J. Magnarella laments that “More than seventy-five percent of the continent's 700 million people live below the poverty line, and ten of the world's thirteen poorest countries are in Africa.”¹⁹ He mentions some elements which comprise the system leading to human rights violations as:

Undeveloped economies, with limited resource bases and insufficient employment/income opportunities for large segments of the population resulting in wide-spread poverty; High population growth rates further straining the natural environment and local resources, while intensifying competition for resources; Ethnic diversity and/or regional factionalism promoting local/particularistic identifications, while hindering the development of a national identification; Ethnic and/or class politics involving competition among leaders of different language, cultural, or regional populations for state positions of political and economic power with the spoils of victory going to supporters; Lack of regime legitimacy as those large segments of the population not culturally and/or politically affiliated with the ruling elite and not sharing in the spoils refuse to recognize the regime as legitimate; Resort to military/police force to maintain power by suppressing political opponents and disgruntled civilians; Violation of economic, civil, and political rights by the regime on the pretext of “national security.”²⁰

Another cause of Human Rights abuses in Nigeria is the potentially dangerous gap in our societies between the young and the old. The young feel that they are ‘used’ to suit the purposes of older people; they feel excluded from power and responsibility. They are not allowed to take part in decision- making and feel those in power do not take into account their needs and hope, even when they constitute a wing of a political party, their lack of meaningful and proper political engagement has sometimes led them to form a sub-culture which may even engage in crime, drug-trafficking, and so on.

The appalling reality is that if one takes a critical look, most African countries share some or all of these elements. This makes the fight against human rights a really cumbersome one. But must we sit down and fold our

arms and bemoan the terrible situation? What roles must religion and religious people play towards ameliorating the human rights situation in Africa?

The Role of Religion in Curtailing Human Rights Abuse

If religion is to be credible, it ought to be relevant and conceptualized. This means that religions in Nigeria should necessarily entail identification with the aspirations, hopes and joys of the African people on one hand, and their anguish, suffering, problems and needs on other hand. Kanyandago, views it from this perspective and elaborates further;

It is important that participants have some personal experiences of the African people. My wish is that every theologian should ask the question: what should I think, say and bear witness to if I were an African theologian. Africans do not require mere pity or mercy or so-called charity. Africans want justice, understanding and solidarity to past injustices, an abuse of human right to be brought to an end. This demands a theology that offers equal partnership in the struggle for total liberation.²¹

The most powerful and urgent concern of religion in Africa is the cry of its citizens. Any religion worth the name must be prepared to listen to them and weigh what they say. It is true as Kanyandago remarks, that “there is poverty, disease, injustice, exploitation, marginalization, isolation, refugees, internally displaced people, persons with disabilities and neglected ethnic and religious minorities in Africa. These are everywhere but not many religions are listening.”²²

As a corollary from the above, our ardent wish is to analyze Africa’s cries for justice and liberation and take a firm stand for humanity. The demands of Jesus and of Christianity in respect of the oppressed, the isolated, and the marginalized should animate all our religious discussions. The injunctions and resolutions of the OAU’s first Ministerial Conference on Human Rights in 1999 are still en vogue today. Among them, the declaration “urges all African states to work assiduously towards the elimination of discrimination against women and the abolition of cultural practices which dehumanize or demean women and children.” Equally, the declaration observed that the promotion and protection of human rights are basically state responsibilities. Thus, it calls on various African countries to establish and adequately fund national human rights institutions and to “engage in a process of continuous dialogue with the African Human Rights Commission.”²³

The “preferential option for the poor” proclaimed by the Synod of Bishops should be actually lived out in Nigeria. The present situation where this option is proclaimed while religious leaders still maintain a closer affinity with the (often oppressive) politico-economic powers that be, and thereby betray this option for the poor; where the abandoned, abused, homeless, exploited and marginalized people are abandoned by their supposed shepherds; where church prelates turn their gaze away from weakness, powerlessness, ‘statuslessness’ and poverty, and often contribute to the victimization and marginalization of her people, must be reconsidered.

It is apt to remember that a Nigerian that has been beaten and battered by chronic economic, demographic, health, and political problems cannot easily achieve the human rights status its people want. There is therefore need for religion to advocate for a new paradigm for development based on a vibrant domestic private sector, a stable state, effective policy analysis, and good governance. Such a paradigm will provide the necessary empowerment needed by the populace and thus drastically reduce the heinous crimes against humanity that reign high today.

Conclusion

There is a sense of hope in the human possibility that what is caused by human action can be changed by same human action or inaction. Human oppression and the powerlessness that resulted into human rights abuses in Nigeria are not unalterable. This calls for a religious response towards the solution of the evil of Human Rights abuse in Nigeria. The objectives and strategies of such a paradigm should be geared towards enabling the oppressed and abused Nigerians to shape power, to participate effectively in the decisions that determine their personal lives in order to correct the horror of Human Rights abuses in Nigeria. Through liberation theology,

Nigerian theologians should address and eradicate enslavements and human rights abuses caused by the international communities and those caused by greedy African leaders. There is need for a cultural revolution directed towards fostering the welfare of Nigerians.

The various religions in Nigeria should insist more on social justice rather than aids as criterion for economic relationships between Nigerians and other nations. African theologians should, by this, develop a theology of human rights that outline the revolution towards the rights of Nigerians to be subjects rather than objects of development. This they can do by constructively challenging the international agencies such as World Bank, World Health Organization (WHO) etc., who limit the goal of development and help to solve the problem of technological backwardness as means of overcoming poverty but do not include plans to abolish or re-order the structures causing dependency. Nigerian theologians, this indeed is our task.

Endnotes

¹P. J. Magnarella, "Preventing Interethnic Conflict and Promoting Human Rights through More Effective Legal, Political, and Aid Structures: Focus on Africa," in *Georgia Journal of International and Comparative Law*, vol. 23. (1993), 329.

²Amnesty International. "1999 Regional Highlights, Africa." Retrieved from www.AI.org. Accessed on 12/09/13.

³Africa Overview. "Human Rights Watch 2000 Report." Retrieved from www.hrw.org. Accessed on 18/08/2013.

⁴O.U. Kalu, *African Christianity: An African Story Perspective on Christ* (Enugu: Snaap Press, 2005), 43.

⁵Oral Interview with Bishop Apochi, M. Catholic Secretariat, Catholic Diocese of Otukpo, April 2008.

⁶M.O. Ekpenyong, "The Church as a Family of God" in *Nacaths Journal of African Theology* vol. 17, (2002), 84.

⁷R. Ejimonye and M. Konye, "The Crisis of Morality in Africa," in *Nacaths Journals of theology* Vol. 17, (2007), 51.

⁸S. Okeke, *Asserting the Unity and Integration of Nigeria* (Awka: Sabina Press, 1998), 69.

⁹Ibid, 28.

¹⁰E.O. Adeleye, *The Challenge of National Integration in Nigeria* (Ibadan: Book builders, 2004), 102.

¹¹C. A. Onuka, *Nigeria: Our Unity in Diversity* (Lagos: Notable Publishers, 2001), 72.

¹²B.N. Inaku, *Integration and Progress in Nigeria: Issues Involved*. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2007), 82.

¹³The African Synod of Bishops. *Relatio Ante Disceptationem* (1994), 4.

¹⁴P. Kanyandago, *Marginalized Africa, An International Perspective* (Kenya: St. Paul's, 2002), 105.

¹⁵Ibid., 58.

¹⁶I. Obi, "African Traditional Values in Dialogue," in *Nacaths Journal of African Theology*, Vol. 17, (2005): 35 - 49.

¹⁷J.H. Cone, *Black Theology and Black Powers* (New York: J.B. Lippincott, 1970), 10.

¹⁸H. Okulu, *Church and Politics in East Africa* (Noirobi: Uzima Press, 1974), 93.

¹⁹Magnarella, *Georgia Journal of International and Comparative Law*, 330.

²⁰Ibid, 331.

²¹Kanyandago, *Marginalized Africa, An International Perspective*, 53.

²²Ibid., 54.

²³P. J. Magnarella, "Achieving Human Rights in Africa: The Challenge for the New Millennium" Retrieved from <http://www.africa.ufl.edu/asq/v4/v4i2a2.htm>. Accessed on 21-08-13.